

A Study the Relationship between Interest and Study Habits of Secondary School Students

Shubhra Chaturvedi¹ and Anshika Jain²

1. Professor, J.V. Jain College, Saharanpur
2. M.Ed Student, J.V. Jain College, Saharanpur, Email : anshijain020@gmail.com

Received : 27/01/2025

1st BPR : 05/02/2025

2nd BPR : 14/02/2025

Accepted : 03/03/2025

Abstract

The present study explores the level of interest and study habit among the secondary school students. Multiphasic Interest Inventory (MII) was administered to measure the interest in different dimensions and the Study Habit test is evaluate a person's typical study behaviors, including how they plan their study time, manage distractions, review materials and approach different learning tasks. This study wants to examine the correlation between Interest and Study Habit of senior secondary school students. Data from 100 students is collected from the senior secondary school in the Saharanpur district of Utter Pradesh, India. Descriptive survey research methods is used for the study, data is collected by random sampling. Multiphasic Interest Inventory (MII) by Dr. (Mrs) S.K. Bawa and Study Habits Test by Dr. Deepti Sharma and Dr. Masaud Ansari. This study found a there is no significant correlation between interest and study habit of secondary students which indicates that interest does not affect study habits but in different dimensions interest affect study habits on secondary level students.

Keywords: Multiphasic Interest Inventory (MII), Study Habits Test.

Introduction

Education is essential in everyone's life. It is the process of acquiring information in many fields and comprehending the surrounding world. Studying is not limited to what one learns in academic institutions, it also involves information gained through life experience and elder generations and generally teenagers students interest affects their study habit. Study habits crucial because they directly impact learning efficiency, retention, and academic success.

Multiphasic Interest Inventory (MII): The Multiphasic Interest Inventory (MII) is a psychological assessment tool designed to measure an individual's interests across multiple domains. While there isn't a widely known standardized MII, the concept aligns with theories in Occupational Interest, Religious Interest, Social Interest, Intellectual Interest, and Recreation Interest. Interest refer to a feeling of curiosity, engagement or concern about a particular subject, activity or topic. It drives individuals to explore, learn and invest time and energy into something they find appealing or valuable. There are several factors that influence a students interest in learning.

Study Habits Test:

An important factor in the growth of knowledge and perception abilities good study habits are essential for academic success. Effective study skills can boost confidence, competence, and self-esteem while also reducing stress related to exams and deadlines. By developing strong study habits, students can optimize their learning process, allowing them to study efficiently in less time and freeing up hours for other activities.

Despite having the necessary intelligence and resources, many students struggle to achieve their expected academic performance. One of the key reasons for this is insufficient time dedicated to studying.

Friedman, A., Friedman, R. (2022): Investigated the effects of hybrid learning environments on learning practics during the COVID-19 outbreak. The findings revealed that flexibility in learning formats led to more individualized study habits but also

highlighted issues of engagement and discipline.

Islam (2021) : conducted a study on study habits, self-esteem, and academic performance among secondary school students in Bangladesh, comparing those in public and private institutions. The results revealed no notable differences in study habits or academic achievement between the two groups. However, the combined influence of study habits and self-esteem explained 12.3% of the variation in academic performance among public school students and 7.5% among private school students.

Schunk, D. H., Zimmerman, B. J. (2020): This comprehensive review discussed how adaptive learning technologies can personalize study habits, allowing students to develop more effective strategies tailored to their individual needs.

Duffy, R. D., Dik, B. J. (2020): Conducted longitudinal studies examining how interests evolve over time and their impacts on career paths, advocating for periodic reassessment using the MII.

Hoque J (2018) A study was conducted to examine the vocational interests of secondary school students in Aligarh in relation to their aspirations. The research employed the Vocational Interest Scale by Dr. Parveen Gegum and the Level of Aspiration Test (LOA) developed by Dr. V. P. Bhargava. Data were analyzed using statistical methods, including Mean, Standard Deviation, and Correlation analysis. The results revealed that there was no significant connection between students' vocational interests and their levels of goals among boys and girls in secondary schools. This study provides valuable insights for teachers, parents, counselors, school administrators, and policymakers in guiding students toward selecting suitable career paths aligned with their interests.

Gandhi. N (2017) A research investigation was carried out to explore the connection between educational interest or the school environment. A randomly selected sample was drawn from various schools in Abohar, Punjab. The Educational Interest Record developed by Dr. S.P. Kulshrestha (2007) was used as the assessment tool. Data analysis was performed using The findings revealed a strong and positive relationship between educational engagement and the school atmosphere.

Statement of the problem

A Study of Relationship between Interest and Study Habit of Secondary School Students.

Objectives

1. To study the relationship between interest and study habit of secondary school students.
2. To study the relationship between occupation interest and study habit of secondary school students.
3. To study the relationship between intellectual interest and study habit of secondary school students.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between interest and study habit of secondary school students.
2. There is no significant relationship between occupation interest and study habit of secondary school students.
3. There is no significant relationship between intellectual interest and study habit of secondary school students.

Delimitation of the study

1. Only one tool is used for measuring Interest.
2. Only one tool is used for measuring Study Habit.
3. The study was restricted to Saharanpur district only.

Research Method Used : This study was conducted by Descriptive survey method.

Population of the study

The population of this study is secondary school students of Saharanpur district.

Sample and sampling technique

In the present study the 100 students studying at secondary level are the sample selected from district Saharanpur by simple random technique through lottery method from two secondary schools.

Variables

Variables used in the present study are : Independent variables: In the present study Interest is the independent variables.

Dependent Variables: In the present study Study Habits is the dependent variables.

Tools used for the study : Research tools are essential as they help researchers achieve their study's aims and objectives. These tools enable researchers to evaluate data effectively, ultimately guiding their decision to accept or reject a research hypothesis. Without research tools, it would become very difficult and time-consuming and it increases the probability of errors. For the study following tools are used for data collection:

1. Multiphasic Interest Inventory: Interest scale by Dr.(Mrs.) S.K.Bawa
2. Study Habits: Study Habits Scale by Dr. Deepti Sharma and Dr. Masaud Ansari.

Statistical Technique used in the study:

Correlation examines the relationship between two or more sets of data to determine whether a connection exists and to quantify the strength of that relationship. The product-moment correlation coefficient (r) is used to quantify the relationship between two variables.

Analysis and Interpretation of the study:

Hypothesis: (1) There is no significant relationship between interest and study habit of secondary school students. A Pearson coefficient of correlation has been computed between two variables.

Table No.1 : Coefficient of correlation between Interest and Study habits of secondary students.

Variables	Size of sample(N)	Coefficient of Correlation (r)	Level of significance
Interest	100	-0.189	Not significant
Study Habits			

Table No.1 shows that interest of secondary students is correlated with study habits as the value coefficient of correlation ' r ' comes to be -0.189

The null hypothesis has been accepted and it has been concluded that the relationship between the interest and study habits of secondary students is not significantly correlated, which means the interest of secondary students does not affect their study habits.

Hypothesis:(2) There is no significant relationship between occupational interest and study habit of secondary school students. A Pearson coefficient of correlation has been computed between two variables.

Table No.2 : Coefficient of correlation between occupational interest and study habits of secondary students.

Variables	N	r	Level of significance
Interest	100	+0.217	Significant at the level of 0.05
Study Habit			

Table No.2 shows that occupational interest of secondary students is not correlated with study habits as the value coefficient of correlation ' r ' comes to be +0.217. The null hypothesis has been rejected and it has been concluded that the relationship between the occupational interest and study habits of secondary students is significantly correlated, which means occupational interest is affect the study habits of secondary students.

Hypothesis:(3) There is no significant relationship between intellectual interest and study habit of secondary school students. A Pearson coefficient of correlation has been computed between two variables.

Table No.3 : Coefficient of correlation between intellectual interest and study habits of secondary students.

Variables	N	r	Level of significance
Interest	100	+0.0804	Not significant
Study Habits			

Table No.3 shows the intellectual interest of secondary students is negative correlated with study habits as the value coefficient of correlation 'r' comes to be +0.080. The null hypothesis has been accepted and it has been concluded that the relationship between the intellectual interest and study habits of secondary students is not significantly correlated, which means the intellectual interest of secondary students does not affect the study habit.

Conclusion and Discussion

- (1) The significant relationship between interest and study habit of secondary school students is not correlate, which indicate that the interest is not affect the study habit of students.
- (2) The significant relationship between the occupational interest and study habits of secondary students is correlated, which means occupational interest is affect the study habits of secondary students.
- (3) The relationship between the intellectual interest and study habits of secondary students is not significantly correlated, which means the intellectual interest not affect the study habit of secondary students.

This study found there is no correlation between interest and study habit of secondary students which indicates that interest does not affect study habit but strong personal interest in a particular area significantly enhances a student's study habits, and different dimensions of interest correlate with study habit. Occupational interest correlate with study habit but intellectual interest does not correlate with study habit which means there can be more aspect which influence intellectual interest of secondary level students.

I have gone through different studies related to study habit and interest and result of these studies demand for a study related to interest and study habit as there is not study on these variables correlated. The interest and study habits of secondary school students be essential to their educational achievement and personal development. So we need to study the relationship between interest and study habit.

References

1. Arnold, K. and Stewart, M. (2008) : Surface Production Operations, Volume 1: Design of Oil and Water Handling Facilities. Elsevier Inc. ISBN: 978-0-7506-7853-7.
2. Arnold, Ken, and Stewart, M. (1999).: Surface Production Operations, Volume 2: Design of Gas-Handling Systems and Facilities. Gulf Professional Publishing, USA.
3. Azevedo L.F.and Gomes G.,(1995). Simple hydrodynamic models for prediction of pig motion in pipelines. Pontificia Universidadie Catholica do Reo de Janerio,1995
4. Azevedo, L. F. A., Bracm, A. M. B., Nieckele, A. O., Naccxhe, M. F., and Gomes, M.G. (1996) "Simple Hydrodynamic Models for the Prediction of Pig Motions in Pipelines." Offshore Technology Conference. 6-9 May, Houston, Texas, USA.
5. Becker, J. R. (1997).: Crude Oil Waxes, Emulsions, and Asphaltenes. PennWell Publishing Company USA.
6. Bello, Kelani Olafinhan, Oyenyin Mufutau B., and Oluyemi, Gbenga Folorunso. (2011): "Minimum Transport Velocity Models for Suspended Particles in Multiphase Flow Revisited." SPE Annual Technical Conference and Exhibition. Society of Petroleum Engineers, 30 October 2 November, Denver, Colorado, USA.
7. Bratland, Ove. (2010).: "Pipe Flow 2: Multi-phase Flow Assurance." Ove Bratland ISBN 978-616-335-926-1,

8. Brennen, Christopher E. (2005): Fundamentals of Multiphase Flows: Cambridge University Press ISBN 0521 848040.
9. Brill, J. P. (2010). Modeling Multiphase Flow in Pipes. *The Way Ahead*, 6(02), 16-17.
10. BS 1042 1 Section 2.1(1983). : Measurement of fluid flow in closed conduits, Method using Pitot Static Tubes, BSI.
11. Banerjee, S. and Chan, A. M. C., (1981). Refilling and rewetting of a hot horizontal tube - 11: Structure of a two-fluid model. *J. Heat Transfer* Vol. 103, pp.287-292.
12. Barua, S., (1982). An experimental verification and modification of the McDonaldBaker pigging model for horizontal flow. MS Thesis U. of Tulsa.
13. Barnea, D. and Taitel, Y., (1986). Flow pattern transition in twophase gas-liquid flows. *Encyclopedia of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 3, Gas Liquid Flows. Gulf Publishing, Houston.
14. Beggs, H. D.,and Brill, J. P., (1973). A study of a two-phase flow in inclined pipes. *Journal of Petroleum Technology*,25, pp. 607-617.
15. Bendiksen, K. H., Brandt, I., Fuchs, P., Linga, H., MaInes, D., and Moe, PL, (1986). Twophase flow research at SINTEF and IFE- some experimental results and a demonstration of the dynamic two-phase flow simulator OLGA. *Offshore Northern Seas Conference*.
16. Bendiksen, K. H., MaInes, D., Moe, and Nuland, S., (1991). The dynamic two-fluid model OLGA: theory and applications. *SPE Production Engng. J.*, pp, 171-180.
17. Cunfiffe, R.S., (1978). Prediction of condensate flow rate in large diameter high pressure wet-gas pipelines. *APEA J.* Vol. 18, pp. 171-177

